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SOLUTION OF FREDHOLM INTEGRAL EQUATIONS OF SECOND KIND USING A COMPOSITE TRIGONOMETRIC FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

An inverse trigonometric function, $x = \sin(\arctan(t))$ was reconstructed to yield a variable transformation function that decays single exponentially with increased number of evaluations N . The new function was used for the approximate solution of Fredholm integral equations of the second kind though a Sinc-collocation procedure. The computational results confirm the exponential error decay that is usually associated with single exponential Sinc methods. The results of the numerical examples presented showed that method is efficient and stable for the defined problem.

KEYWORDS:

Composite trigonometric function, Sinc collocation, Fredholm integral equations, algebraic equations, trapezoidal rule

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INTRODUCTION

We consider the Fredholm integral equations of the second kind of the form

$$u(x) = \lambda \int_a^b k(x,t)u(t)dt + g(x), \quad a \leq x \leq b \quad (1)$$

in this paper to determine the approximate solution u for a given scalar λ with k and g as smooth functions, Wazwaz (2011).

The solution of various types of integral equations has previously been considered by other authors where the $\tanh$ function or the $\tanh - \sinh$ function was widely used to construct single exponential and double exponential formula respectively. these works are extensively illustrated in the articles listed below: Rashidinia & Zarebnia(2005), Rashidinia, J. & Zarebnia, M. (2008), Okayama, T., Matsuo, T. and Sugihara, M. (2011), Mohsen, A. and El-Gamel, M. (2014), Eno John & Nkem Ogbonna (2016), Maleknejad, K., Rostami Y., & Kalalagh, H. (2016) and John, E. D. (2016).

Recent contributions extend the application of Sinc collocation method to areas such as: integro-differential equations, classes of integral equations, boundary value problems and partial differential equations. These are well documented in Okayama, T. (2023), Mehdi J. *et al*(2023), Li M. *et al* (2023) and Zabihi Fatemeh (2024).

2.0 PRELIMINARIES

2.1 Approximation on the Real Line

This procedure relies is the transformation function

Let

$$T_h = h \sum_{j=-\infty}^{\infty} F(jh), h > 0 \quad (2)$$

be the trapezoidal rule approximation to the integral

$$I = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(u) du \quad (3)$$

If the function $F(u)$ is defined on the whole real line, $(-\infty, \infty)$

$$F(u) \approx \sum_{j=-N}^N F(jh)S(j, h)(u), \quad u \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(u) du \approx \sum_{j=-N}^N F(jh) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(j, h)(u) du = h \sum_{j=-N}^N F(jh) \quad (5)$$

where

the function

$$S(j, h)(t) = S\left(\frac{t}{h} - j\right) = \frac{\sin\pi\left(\frac{t}{h} - j\right)}{\pi\left(\frac{t}{h} - j\right)}, j = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (6)$$

is known as Sinc function Stenger (1993), such that for $t_k = kh$,

$$S(j, h)(kh) = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq j \\ 1, & k = j \end{cases}$$

2.2 Approximation on a Finite Interval $\Lambda = (a, b)$

Let $x = \varphi(t)$, then by change of variables, the integral

$$I = \int_a^b f(x)dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\varphi(t))\varphi'(t)dt \tag{7}$$

Considering equations (2) and (6) above

$$I = \int_a^b f(x)dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\varphi(t))\varphi'(t)dt \approx h \sum_{j=-N}^N f(\varphi(jh))\varphi'(jh). \tag{8}$$

In this work, we defined as the transformation function as

$$x = \varphi(t) = \sin(\arctan(t)), t \in \mathbb{R} \tag{9}$$

having an algebraic expression

$$\varphi(t) = \frac{t}{\sqrt{1+t^2}} \tag{10}$$

For some constant α , we can rewrite as

$$x = \sin\left(\arctan\left(\frac{t}{\sqrt{\alpha}}\right)\right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\alpha t^{-2}}} \tag{11}.$$

For the purpose of our discussion, let us replace t with an exponential expression e^t , and from (11), we have

$$x = \varphi(t) = \sin\left(\arctan\left(\frac{e^t}{\sqrt{\alpha}}\right)\right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\alpha e^{-2t}}}, t \in (-\infty, \infty) \tag{12}$$

so that $\varphi(-\infty, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1)$.

Generally, for the finite interval (a, b) and $\varphi(-\infty, \infty) \rightarrow (a, b)$, with the following expressions,

$$x = \varphi(t) = a + \frac{b-a}{\sqrt{1+\alpha e^{-2t}}}, \tag{13}$$

$$x' = \varphi'(t) = \frac{(b-a)\alpha e^{-2t}}{(1+\alpha e^{-2t})^{3/2}} \quad (14)$$

and

$$t = \varphi^{-1}(x) = \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{\alpha(x-a)^2}{(b+x-2a)(b-x)} \right) \quad (15)$$

with the Sinc points x_j given by

$$x_j = \varphi(t_j) = \varphi(jh), j = -N, \dots, N. \quad (16)$$

For $a = 0, b = 1$ and $\alpha = 3$, equation (13) reduces to

$$x = \varphi(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+3e^{-2t}}} \quad (17)$$

The composite trigonometric function introduced in this paper compares favourably with the $\tanh$ function, Maleknejad, K. *et al* (2016) in terms of convergence but slower when compared to that of error function, John, E. D. *et al*, (2024). They are all classified as single exponential functions.

2.3 Convergence Theorems for Single Exponential Sinc Approximation

Definition 2.1 Okayama *et al* (2011)

Let α be a positive constant, and let D be a bounded and simply-connected domain which satisfies $(a, b) \subset D$. Then $L_\alpha(D)$ denotes the family of functions f that satisfy the following conditions: (i) f is analytic in D ; (ii) there exists a constant C such that for all z in D

$$|f(z)| \leq C|Q(z)|^\alpha \quad (18)$$

where the function Q is defined by

$$Q(z) = (z-a)(b-z).$$

For the implementation of the single exponential transformation in the above Definition 2.1, the domain D considered to be the region $\varphi(D_d) = \{z = \varphi(\mu): \mu \in D_d\}$ where $D_d = \{z \in \mathbb{C}: |\operatorname{Im} \mu| < d\}$ denotes a strip region of width $2d$. This gives the image of the region under consideration as,

$$\varphi(D_d) = \left\{ z \in \mathbb{C} : \left| \arg \frac{1}{2} \log \left(\frac{\alpha(x-a)^2}{(b+x-2a)(b-x)} \right) \right| < d \right\}. \quad (19)$$

Theorem 1 Stenger (1993)

Let $f \in L_\alpha \varphi(D_d)$ for d with $0 < d < \pi$, let N be a positive integer and let h be selected by the formula

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{\pi d}{\alpha N}}$$

then there is a constant C independent of N , such that

$$\max_{a \leq x \leq b} \left| f(x) - \sum_{j=-N}^N f(\varphi(jh)) S(j, h) (\{\varphi\}^{-1}(x)) \right| \leq C \sqrt{N} e^{-\sqrt{\pi d \alpha N}}. \quad (20)$$

The choice of h is optimal and satisfies (20) based on Sugihara (1997).

Theorem 2 Okayama *et al*(2010)

Let $(fQ) \in L_\alpha \varphi(D_d)$ for d with $0 < d < \pi$, let N be a positive integer and let h be selected by the formula

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{\pi d}{\alpha N}}$$

then there is a constant C independent of N , such that

$$\left| \int_a^b f(t) dt - h \sum_{j=-N}^N f(\varphi(jh)) S(j, h) (\{\varphi\}'(jh)) \right| \leq C e^{-\sqrt{\pi d \alpha N}} \quad (21)$$

Definition 2.2 Okayama *et al* (2010)

Let D be a bounded and simply connected domain, the we denote by $HC(D)$ the family of all functions that are analytic in D and continuous in $\bar{D}$. The function space is complete with the norm $\|\cdot\|_{HC(D)}$ defined by

$$\|f\|_{HC(D)} = \max_{z \in \bar{D}} |f(z)|. \quad (22)$$

Definition 2.3 Stenger (2000)

Let α be a constant with $0 < \alpha < 1$ and let D be a bounded and simply connected domain such that $(a, b) \subset D$. Then the space $M_\alpha(D)$ consists of all functions f that satisfies the following conditions

- (i) $f \in HC(D)$;
- (ii) there exists a constant C for all z in D such that

for

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(z) &= \exp(\varphi^{-1}(z)), \\ |f(z) - f(a)| &= O(|\rho(z)|^\alpha) \text{ as } z \rightarrow a, \\ |f(z) - f(b)| &= O(|\rho(z)|^\alpha) \text{ as } z \rightarrow b. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

According to Stenger (1993), the translated function

$$T[f](x) = f(x) - \frac{f(a) + \rho(x)f(b)}{1 + \rho(x)} \in L_\alpha(D) \quad (24)$$

if $f \in M_\alpha(D)$ and the approximation

$$T[f](x) \approx \sum_{j=-N}^N T[f](\varphi(jh)S(j, h)(\varphi^{-1}(x_j))). \quad (25)$$

Combining equations (24) and (25),

$$f(x) \approx P_N[f](x) = \sum_{j=-N}^N T[f](\varphi(jh)S(j, h)(\varphi^{-1}(x_j))) + \frac{f(a) + \rho(x)f(b)}{1 + \rho(x)}. \quad (26)$$

Let the auxiliary basis function be defined by

$$\tau_a(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \rho(x)}, \tau_b(x) = \frac{\rho(x)}{1 + \rho(x)}, \quad (27)$$

then the generalized approximation to $f(x)$ is of the form

$$P_N[f](x) = f(a)\tau_a(x) + \sum_{j=-N}^N T[f](\varphi(jh)S(j, h)(\varphi^{-1}(x_j))) + f(b)\tau_b(x). \quad (28)$$

Theorem 3

Let $f \in M_\alpha(\varphi(D_d))$ for d with $0 < d < \pi$, let N be a positive integer and h defined as

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{\pi d}{\alpha N}}$$

then there exists a constant C independent of N such that

$$\|f - P_N f\|_{C([a,b])} \leq C\sqrt{N}e^{-\sqrt{\pi d a N}} \tag{29}$$

Remark: this condition holds since φ is a single exponential function.

3.0 THE SINC COLLOCATION METHOD

Let $u(x) \in M_\alpha(\varphi(D))$ and $u_N(x)$ be the exact and approximate solution of (1), while $u(x_j)$ and u_j are the exact and approximate solutions at a sinc point x_j respectively.

According to Okayama *et al* (2010),

$$u(x) = u(x_{-N-1})w_a(x) + \sum_{j=-N}^N u(x_j)S(j, h)(\{\varphi\}^{-1}(x)) + u(x_{N+1})w_b(x) \tag{30}$$

will satisfy (1) at Sinc points of φ , since it is a linear combination of the sinc functions $S(j, h)(t)$ and the auxiliary basis functions $\tau_a(x)$ and $\tau_b(x)$. Here, the basis functions are considered to be fixed and the collocation points defined as

$$x_i = \begin{cases} a, & i = -N - 1 \\ \varphi(ih), & i = -N \dots N \\ b, & i = N + 1 \end{cases} \tag{31}$$

With the collocation points defined as above, we set the approximate solution u of (1) as

$$u_N(x) = u_{-N-1}w_a(x) + \sum_{j=-N}^N u_j S(j, h)(\{\varphi\}^{-1}(x)) + u_{N+1}w_b(x) \tag{32}$$

and the integral in (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b k(x, t)u(t)dt \\ &= K[w_a](x)u_{-N-1} + h \sum_{j=-N}^N k(x, t_j)\varphi(jh)u_j + K[w_b](x)u_{N+1} \\ &+ Oe^{-\frac{\pi d}{h}} \end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Noting that $S(j, h)(\{\varphi\}^{-1}(x_k)) = S(j, h)(\{\varphi\}^{-1}(\varphi(kh))) = S(j, h)(kh) = \delta_{kj}$.

with

$$K[f](x) = h \sum_{j=-N}^N k(x, t_j) f(x_j) \phi(jh). \quad (34)$$

Using (32)- (34) in (1), we obtain the collocation formula as

$$\begin{aligned} & \{w_a(x_k) - K[w_a](x_k)\}u_{-N-1} + \sum_{j=-N}^N \delta_{kj} - hk(x_k, t_j) \phi(jh) u_j \\ & + \{w_b(x_k) - K[w_b](x_k)\}u_{N+1} \\ & = g(x_k) \quad (35) \end{aligned}$$

representing a $(2N + 3) \times (2N + 3)$ system of linear equations,

$$(E_n - K_n)u_n = g_n \quad (36)$$

in compact form

with

$$E_n = w_a(x_k) + \sum_{j=-N}^N S(j, h) (\{\phi\}^{-1}(x_k)) + w_b(x_k)$$

$$K_n = K[w_a](x_k) + h \sum_{j=-N}^N k(x_k, t_j) \phi(jh) + K[w_b](x_k)$$

$$g_n = [g(a), g(x_{-N}), \dots, g(x_N), g(b)]^T$$

$$u_n = [u_{-N-1}, u_{-N}, \dots, u_N, u_{N+1}]^T.$$

By solving the above system of equations for u_n and using the result in (32), we obtain the approximate solution $u_N(x)$ to (1).

4.0 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Some examples are presented in this section illustrate the implementation of the sinc collocation procedure (13). In the following calculations, $\lambda = 1$ from (2) and following

Sugihara (1997), $\alpha = 1, d = \frac{\pi}{2}$ with the step size $h = \sqrt{\frac{\pi d}{\alpha N}}$.

The maximum absolute error between the exact solution $u(x)$ and the approximate solution $u_N(x)$ at sinc points x_k given by $|E_N(h(\varphi))|$ such that with respect to L_∞ norm,

$$|E_N(h(\varphi))| = \max_{k = -N - 1, -N, \dots, N, N + 1} |u(x_k) - u_N(x_k)|. \quad (37)$$

The numerical stability of the method is monitored using the condition number $\kappa(Z)$ of the coefficient matrix $Z = E_n - K_n$ of the system (36) based on infinity norm and defined by

$$\kappa(Z) = \|Z\|_\infty \|Z^{-1}\|_\infty. \quad (38)$$

The computations were carried out using MATLAB® software.

Example 1 Rahbar and Hashemizadeh (2008)

$$f(x) = - \int_0^1 \sqrt{xy} f(y) dy + \sqrt{x} \quad (39)$$

with exact solution

$$u(x) = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{x}.$$

Example 2 Rashidinia and Zarebnia (2005)

$$u(x) = \int_0^1 e^{xt} u(t) dt + e^x + \frac{e^{x+1} - 1}{x + 1} \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1 \quad (40)$$

with exact solution

$$u(x) = e^x.$$

Table 1

$|E_N(h(\varphi))|$ and $\kappa(Z)$ for Example 1

$|E_N(h(\varphi))|$ and $\kappa(Z)$ for Example 2

N	$ E_N(h(\varphi)) $	$\kappa(Z)$	$ E_N(h(\varphi)) $	$\kappa(Z)$
10	1.7027×10^{-6}	6.9×10^0	1.2×10^{-3}	2.1×10^1
20	3.1632×10^{-8}	6.9×10^0	8.6471×10^{-5}	2.1×10^1

30	3.6932×10^{-10}	6.9×10^0	9.7520×10^{-6}	2.1×10^1
40	1.4715×10^{-11}	6.9×10^0	1.5240×10^{-6}	2.1×10^1
50	1.8985×10^{-14}	6.9×10^0	2.9600×10^{-7}	2.1×10^1

Fig. 1. Exact and approximate solution of Example 1 when $N = 40$.

Fig. 2. Exact and approximate solution of Example 2 when $N = 40$.

4.0 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Sinc collocation method is a continuing field of studies in numerical analysis and its application covers a wide range of scientific research relating to integral equations, differential equations and integro-differential equations. It is a robust scheme with advantages over procedure based on polynomial basis functions with regards to rate of convergence.

Our work in this paper was to demonstrate the implementation of a new single exponential function for the solution of Fredholm integral equations of the second kind. It can be easily extended to other forms of integral and differential equations. Already similar works has been done with different variable transformation functions.

The results of the application of Sinc method using composite trigonometric function for Fredholm integral equations of the second kind was demonstrated with Examples 1 and 2 above. The decay of error values as shown in Table 1 indicates improvement of the approximate value as N increases. In Figures 1 and 2, the closeness of the exact solution and the approximate solution is seen when $N = 40$. Furthermore, the stability of the scheme is established from the observations of the condition number $\kappa(Z)$ of the linear system of equations arising from Sinc collocation method based on the composite trigonometric function. For Example 1, $\kappa(Z) \leq 6.93$, and for Example 2, $\kappa(Z) \leq 21$ for all values of N considered. These values remain steady over this range of values showing that the procedure is not unstable following minor changes.

Finally, the implementation of the composite trigonometric function for this purpose is shown to be efficient from the numerical results obtained, which also indicates that the composite trigonometric function introduced here is a single exponential function. Investigation on the modification to further improve convergence of this scheme is ongoing.

The authors will welcome constructive reviews and contributions that will help further the research regarding the formula implemented in this article.

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